

1. Introduction

The main purpose of the New Ukrainian School is to help to reveal and develop them (skills, abilities, and opportunities) on the basis of partnership between teachers, pupils and parents.

The above makes it possible to determine the need and feasibility of studying the system of work of parents and the school to create conditions for the formation of subject competencies of elementary school pupils in the process of studying specific disciplines. In the context of the author's work "Design and Technology" [1].

Since the formation and development of primary school-children takes place under NUS conditions, and the school is part of the living environment of all participants in the educational process, it is the primary school and each family that act as social institutions, and for the child they are the unit of its safe stay at school.

Analyzing the work of Ukrainian and foreign teachers, psychologists, and primary education specialists, it should be noted that the implementation of the humanistic principle is the basis for the organization of the educational process. The authors, on a humanistic basis and a human centric psychological approach, demonstrate the real benefits of interaction in the modern education system. In addition, they offer specific ways and methods of interaction between teacher and pupils [2]. J. Raven, describing the motivated ability to interact at a high level of trust, mutual understanding, a creative approach to business, defines competency not only as an indicator of professionalism. Revealing the other side of competence, the scientist talks about personality-specific indicators – to act together, make decisions freely, and actively influence the interaction process [3]. E. Bern, revealing the psychology of human relations, focuses on the system of games, exercises, forms of work, providing systematic work on the organization of interactions between participants in the interaction [4]. O. Savchenko offers the principles of social dialogue on the basis of equality of interaction, partnership [5]. O. Galian based on the selection and implementation of educational technologies shows the influence of a monological and dialogical paradigm in the subject, the activity of participants in the educational process [6]. L. Khomich reveals the features of professional activities of primary school teachers, the basic functions of primary education teachers, affecting the development of the pupil personality [7].

PECULIARITIES OF IMPLEMENTING THE PARTNERSHIP PRINCIPLE IN THE FORMATION OF SUBJECT COMPETENCIES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS

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Abstract: The reorientation of the modern school to the conditions of partnership, cooperation, interaction, equality and systematicity in the educational process leads to the development of key and subject competencies that become important and decisive values of the New Ukrainian School. Each child is a unique, independent, creative person, endowed with abilities and opportunities, the development of which should be supported and increased by both the family and the school.

The famous Ukrainian teacher, academician O. Savchenko, in the pedagogy of partnership of the New Ukrainian School, determined the principles of social partnership. In her opinion, the constructive model of interaction between the family and the school, on the one hand, provides for productive and responsible models of behavior between family, children and teachers, combining respect, trust, dialogue, volunteerism, equality and responsibility, and on the other hand provides opportunities for improving the educational process, educational activities and systematic work on the study of subject competencies.

A means of creating a new educational environment is the formation of the subject competencies of younger pupils in the process of studying the "Design and Technology" course.

Four-year students of the Faculty of Psychology and Education, majoring in primary education, were actively involved in the system work, they actively prepared, organized, and conducted a lesson on the subject of "Making viburnum twigs using quilling technique".

The most effective and interesting forms for parents, children, and teachers turned out to be forms that demonstrated their attitude to their own children, expressed a desire to help, and provided a developing environment during the lesson.

The experience of primary school teachers shows that the implementation of the partnership principle, as of now the problem is relevant and timely for primary education, the family and the New Ukrainian School as a whole.

Keywords: NUS, design and technology, partnership, future teacher, elementary school pupil, competency.

As experience shows, an important component of such work is the study of the personality of pupils. This allows to control not only the process, but also the pace of their mental development (cognitive, emotional-volitional sphere, creative abilities, motivated abilities to be included in educational activities). According to the author, interesting in this area of work is the creation of a new educational environment in which pupils and teachers and parents are comfortable. It is in such an environment that each person functions freely. It is in demand, it feels security and most importantly, it is satisfied and happy. The issues of ensuring such an environment are dealt with by Ya. Kamensky – concerned the problems of the educational environment in which participants in the process experience pleasure, support and security [8]. A. Makarenko is the author of the principle of pedagogical interaction and has shown the stages of the formation of the collective and pupil, including [9]. V. Sukhomlynskyi is organized educational activities giving heart to children and directing the actions of teachers and pupils to solve common problems [10]. I. Bekh describes a personality-oriented education recognizes responsibility as the main feature in the activity of the child. With the help of it, the pupil seeks to achieve a useful goal, is able to realize its actions and coordinate its behavior with the requirements of society [11]. I. Synytsia reveals the essence of pedagogical tact, insisted on the ability to build relationships between teacher and pupil, leader and subordinate on the principles of mutual trust, mutual assistance and cooperation [12].

A means of organizing such work is the formation of the subject competencies of younger pupils in the process of studying the "Design and Technology" course.

The purpose of teaching design and technology is to develop a child's personality by means of subject-transformative activities, the formation of key and design and technological competencies necessary to solve life problems in interaction with others, cultural and national self-expression.

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2. Material and Methods

The content of the program has the potential for the formation of eleven key competencies in primary education applicants [1].

Common to all key competencies are the following skills: reading with understanding, the ability to express one's opinion

verbally and in writing, critical and systemic thinking, creativity, initiative, the ability to logically substantiate a position, the ability to constructively manage emotions, assess risks, make decisions, solve problems, and collaborate with other persons taking into account the integrated nature of competence in the learning process [1].

And the content of subject competencies in the field of natural sciences, engineering and technology, which include the formation of curiosity, the desire to seek and propose new ideas, to observe and research independently or in a group, formulate assumptions and draw conclusions based on the experiments, know yourself and the world around you by observing and research [1].

During pedagogical practice, future primary school teachers (students of the psychological and pedagogical faculty of Kryvyi Rih State Pedagogical University, majoring in primary education aged 20–21. The total number of participants is 20 years old) demonstrate not only theoretical knowledge on “Methods of teaching labor training with a practical training” (compilation of a lesson, rules of the safety technique, elements of graphic literacy for further work with instructional and technological maps). Also, practical skills in developing practical competencies in elementary schoolchildren during the development of the “Design and Technology” discipline (3rd class).

The effectiveness of the organization of such a process, the quality of professional tasks depends on well-coordinated systemic work between all participants in the educational interaction (future teachers, served as assistant teachers of primary school, teachers, pupils and their parents).

The organization of systematic work consists in the fact that cooperation, interaction in choosing a strategy, ways to achieve goals, established specific community of interests, responsible attitude towards oneself and others, is the creation of a developing environment for each participant in the process by deploying productive learning activities.

3. Result

The students of the Faculty of Psychology and Pedagogy, thanks to systematic work with parents due to increased cooperation between parents, children and the pedagogical team, were able to track the needs and demands of modern parents, their level of pedagogical competence, awareness, willingness to create; teachers’ experience, their level of professional training, creativity and creativity in the implementation of practical tasks, adaptation to new NUS conditions, adequacy to the perception of criticism, the desire to accept new things, share their best practices, learn from their colleagues and constantly improve their qualification level and psychological culture. It is these positions that allowed future teachers to create an atmosphere of family and school cooperation, mutual understanding between parents, teachers and pupils, while increasing the level of communication culture, dialogue among all participants of the educational process, without exception.

Teachers, parents and students worked actively in this direction, organizing not only the educational process, but also realizing all types of activity: role-playing games, emotional dialogues with parents, psychological and pedagogical living rooms, interesting meetings, parent weeks, parental lessons, blitz tournaments, evenings of “questions and answers”.

The most effective and interesting ways for parents, children, and teachers turned out to be forms of working with families that demonstrated the attitude of parents to their own children and, most importantly, the opportunity for each child to write to mother, father, and teacher.

The experience of primary school teachers shows that the problem of partnership is known to modern teachers, relevant for primary schools and can be implemented in the course of solving both educational and educational problems. Let’s find interesting developments in this direction among teachers of Kryvyi Rih, Dnipropetrovsk region.

They focus on fulfilling the main task in such cooperation, namely, to bring cooperation, mutual communication, mutual assistance and cooperation between family and school as close as possible.

According to the author, the experience of the elementary school teacher, lyceum No. 11, is interesting. Novohrad-Volynsky, Zhytomyr Region, Ukraine – L. Mykytenko, who is sure that parents must go to school with their children. The Paternity School works for them, which brings together: Parent meeting – consultations, Tête-à-tête parent meeting, Demonstration lessons for parents, Joint lessons with parents, Tea drinking meeting.

Let’s dwell in more detail on such a form of work as the Parent meeting – consultations. This way of communication allows the teacher to explain to parents the material on the topic that their children will learn. Moreover, the supply of educational material to parents is proposed by the same methods as the pupils (setting a problem, finding a method, applying the method, working in pairs, groups). Parents for some time become “pupils”, taking on their roles, the problems of children are closer and more understandable for them. In addition, parents become informed, acting as consultants, and therefore, our colleagues [13].

It was this approach that the author was implementing when organizing a system of lessons for parents in the process of studying the “Design and Technology” course.

Let’s give a fragment of a lesson in the third class on the topic “Making viburnum twigs using quilling technique”. The lesson was held in several stages. At the first stage – preparatory, parents introduced the children to the features of this art form; with elements of quilling technology, together prepared materials for the manufacture of products.

Quilling or paper filigree is the art of making exquisite, almost lace products by twisting spirals of long and narrow strips of paper.

“Quilling” comes from the English word “quill”, which means “bird feather”. Its reliable origin is unknown. According to some sources, paperwork appeared in China after the invention of paper, and according to others – in ancient Egypt.

In fact, quilling was documented for the first time in 1500. This is the period when French and Italian nuns used thin opaque paper and goose feathers to decorate religious paintings. The use of goose feathers gave rise to the name “quilling”.

In Europe and England, among women of high society, this art became popular only at the end of 1600. They used this exotic technique to create jewelry, as well as to exquisitely decorate boxes, baskets, furniture, vases, candlesticks and other things. Such an exotic art form was done only by wealthy people [14].

At the second – the main stage, the children worked according to the instruction card “Viburnum twig”. At this stage, they showed activity – the teacher and the future teacher, the parents performed the role of assistant.

Viburnum twig

To make a twig of viburnum, it is necessary to choose a base – cardboard and three colors of strips: red – 17 pcs., green – 14, brown – 2.

A tool for twisting of rolls is a rod, glue is needed to fix the rolls.

Let's start with the manufacture of the twig itself. On the base, let's randomly attach a strip of brown, but approximately like a viburnum twig. Let's attach small pieces of brown color to the main twig – these will be the twigs on which let's place leaves and berries of viburnum.

Next, let's produce tight red roles – berries. Let's twist the strip, pull out the rod and fix the tip of the strip with glue. Let's will make 17 such berries.

Now let's begin to make leaflets. Let's twist the roll, pull out the core, let the roll unfold and fix the tip of the strip with glue. Then let's take the roll and squeeze it with the thumb and forefinger of both hands to form the "eye" element.

The third stage is the final one, "Making a viburnum twig". When all the details are ready, let's proceed to the design of the brush of berries and leaves. At this stage, all participants in the lesson have the opportunity to show creativity, spontaneity, freedom of choice to design a viburnum twig.

Organization of systematic work by students of the specialty Primary education during pedagogical practice has shown the effectiveness of this approach in building relationships between teachers, pupils and parents. Interesting and informative lessons for parents, parental weeks, one-on-one parent meetings, etc. allowed to show flexibility and a desire to cooperate with children, parents and teachers.

4. Discussion

After analyzing the ideas of social partnership developed by O. Savchenko and using the principle of social partnership

defined by her, the main task of the author of the article was in the interaction of family and school [5].

An important component of the educational process of NUS is the organization of work with parents and families of pupils. The author is convinced that only under the condition of purposeful and productive cooperation of teachers, children and their families can decisively return to the personality of the child. To the development of its responsibility as an integral property of personality, it is formed only in a situation of choice and freedom. I. Bekh recognizes responsibility as crucial in the activities of the child. With the help of which pupils strive to achieve a certain goal, they self-see their own actions, voluntarily coordinate their behavior with the requirements of society [11]. The aforementioned quality in the pedagogical format is taken as the basis for the formation of subject competencies.

The results can be used in the design of the educational process in the conditions of NUS based on the implementation of the principle of partnership interaction. The most striking result in practical activities (using the quilling technique) and in the theoretical direction (searching for information, fulfilling the roles of parents – "consultant", "scientist") developed a lesson for parents on the topic "Making viburnum twigs using quilling technique" in the process of studying "Design and technology" subject.

It was advisable in the system of work to propose to submit notes, instruction cards on the use of other techniques in the study of "Design and Technology", as well as detailed development of lessons from the above course.

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